

Strengthening Character Through Strengthening the Pancasila Student Profile (P5) and Rahmatan lil Alamin Student Profile (P2RA) at MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City

Alya Dinia Asyfiqi Masykur¹, Abdul Haris², Syamsurizal Yazid³

¹Master of Islamic Religious Education, University of Muhammadiyah Malang, Indonesia

^{2,3} University of Muhammadiyah Malang, East Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe character strengthening through the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) and Rahmatan Lil Alamin Student Profile (P2RA) activities at MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City. This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study research type. Data analysis uses the Miles, Huberman and Saldana data analysis test and data validity test using triangulation. Data collection techniques through observation during the activity, interviews with the curriculum vice principal, facilitator team, and students, and documentation in the form of supporting data such as project modules and activity photos. The results of this study indicate that at the planning stage, the principal represented by the curriculum vice principal determines the implementation time, forms a facilitator team, determines the theme, and creates a project module by the facilitator team. At the implementation stage, it is carried out for four weeks with details of introduction and presentation to students, group formation and discussion, preparation of products to be produced, and finally an exhibition. At the evaluation stage, what is done is peer assessment and the final product produced is successful or not.

KEYWORDS:

character, project, student profil

1. INTRODUCTION

One effect of the rapid changes in the era is the reduction in pupils' good character. The low degree of Pancasila values' interpretation and application in daily life has an impact on this. In light of these considerations, the government is ultimately urged to act right away and continue to monitor the ongoing changes brought about by the creation of the national curriculum (Nur'aini 2023).

The curriculum needed to be revitalized, and the adjustment was done since it was thought to be out of line with the intended expectations (Febriani, Azizah, and Setiawati 2022). The introduction of the autonomous curriculum was one outcome of the curriculum renewal. In accordance with the Pancasila Student Profile, the Independent Curriculum was created as a curriculum that emphasizes not just academic

excellence but also the development of students' character and soft skills through project-based learning.

Through the Rahmatan Lil Alamiin Student Profile, or P2RA, and the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project, or P5, the Madrasah curriculum also contributes to the development of students' character in accordance with the Merdeka Curriculum. One unique aspect of the cross-disciplinary project completed in Madrasah is the inclusion of P2RA in the Pancasila student profile (Nur'aini 2023).

One feature of the cross-disciplinary project carried out in the Madrasah is the inclusion of rahmatan lil alamiin values in the Pancasila student profile (Nur'aini 2023). The skills that need to be developed include problem-solving abilities, critical thinking, communication skills, teamwork, creativity and new innovations, accurate information insights, fulfilling responsibilities as God's creatures, and interreligious tolerance (Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Islam 2022).

The goal of P5 and P2RA is to help Pancasila students develop their character profiles. According to Aprilia et al. (2024), the profile comprises six dimensions: (1) faith, devotion to God Almighty, and noble morals; (2) independence; (3) mutual cooperation; (4) global diversity;

Corresponding Author: Alya Dinia Asyfiqi Masykur

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(5) critical thinking; and (6) creativity. It also elaborates on the need for students to apply religious values in a moderate manner (Aprila et al. 2024).

Nadiem Makarim introduced the idea of independent learning, which may be distilled into a few key ideas. (1) One way for teachers to overcome the challenges they have in their current teaching practices is through independent study. (2) The workload of teachers is lessened, they are allowed to create cumbersome administration, and they are given latitude in assembling evaluation tools. (3) Interested in learning about the challenges that educators experience in the classroom, challenges that new students face, challenges that teachers face in preparing to teach, learning activities, and evaluation issues like USBN-UN. (4) Through education, teachers contribute significantly to the nation's future development. As a result, it is crucial to make every learning process enjoyable and happy (Khoirurrijal et al. 2022).

Three points can be used to characterize project implementation in educational units: In terms of content, activities, and implementation time, (a) it is a co-curricular activity, or it can be incorporated into intracurricular and extracurricular activities; (b) it is flexible; and (c) educational units can collaborate with the community and/or the workplace to create and carry out projects (Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Islam 2022).

The actual facts show that there have been numerous modifications in the way that character education has been included into the learning process. This is because there is a moral and character problem among the younger generation in schools (Wulandari, Taufik, and Kuncahyono 2018). It is inevitable that all aspects of education, including schools, teachers, and students, will need to adapt and adjust to changes in the curricular framework. Since the Ministry of Education and Culture does not mandate that this independent curriculum be implemented directly in every school due to the need for school readiness, which is obviously different, it has been implemented gradually rather than uniformly in all schools (Usman et al. 2023). The Decree of the Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology Number 162/M/2021 concerning driving schools contains the regulations governing the implementation of the independent curriculum. It stipulates that the curriculum is not implemented simultaneously and in large quantities, which is in line with the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology's policy that gives educational units flexibility in how they implement the curriculum.

Although the independent curriculum was supposed to be a solution to today's educational issues, it nevertheless presents a number of challenges, particularly for teachers who carry out the learning activities in the classroom (Falah, Safrizal, and Sunarti 2023). The following are the challenges that teachers face when implementing the P5 program in schools: (1) teacher preparedness for P5 implementation; (2) restricted resources; (3) time and infrastructure; and (4) a lack of

teachers for P5 implementation and preparation training (Nabila, Andriana, and Rokmanah 2023). As of right now, the autonomous curriculum is still being established and is a heated topic of discussion, particularly in relation to character development through the Rahmatan Lil Alamin Students (P2RA) and Pancasila Student Profile development Project (P5) in educational institutions.

The goal of character education is to awaken the spirit that is inside people on a cognitive, affective, and psychomotor level. Character education, on the other hand, is an endeavour to create a culture by offering instruction for children's soul and body development in accordance with their nature, as well as an atmosphere that influences mental and physical advancement towards human morals, according to Ki Hajar Dewantara, the father of National Education (Hikmasari, Susanto, and Syam 2021).

It is necessary to strengthen pupils' character in order to prepare them to become people with strong personalities through education. Education is a deliberate attempt to guide and educate someone so they can become a self-sufficient, responsible, creative, knowledgeable, healthy, and honourable human being on a physical and spiritual level (Tsauri 2015).

Lickona outlined a number of reasons why character education is crucial, including: a lack of understanding of moral principles that harm one another; the primary purpose of civilisation is to instill moral principles in the next generation; the significance of schools in delivering character education to counteract the minimal moral instruction from parents and society; moral principles that are still universal and acceptable, such as responsibility, attention, etc.; the significance of comprehending the idea of democracy "from, for, and by society"; teaching positive values and culture; dedication to character education; because when character education is consistently cultivated, supported, and fostered, schools become more civilised (Hikmasari, Susanto, and Syam 2021).

Formal Education Units, also known as schools, are groups of educational services that organise formal, structured, and tiered education. They include kindergartens (TK), elementary education units, and secondary education units organised by the central government, regional governments, and the community, according to the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education in Formal Education Units (Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, and Indonesia 2018).

In order to execute learning activities for a Character Education Strengthening program in schools, the principal and instructors must work together. While teachers are responsible for establishing and familiarising students with character values in the classroom and school environment to help them develop the necessary character, the administrator is responsible for creating a school culture that will make the

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school stand out from the competition (Maisaro, Wiyono, and Arifin 2018).

According to Permendikbud No. 20 of 2018 article 6 paragraph 2, character strengthening in schools or class-based approaches must be carried out by: devising local content curricula based on the needs and characteristics of the region, educational units, and students; planning class management and learning/guidance methods according to the character of students; conducting learning/guidance evaluations; and integrating character values into the learning process thematically or integrated into subjects according to the curriculum content.

Therefore, in order to be implemented in accordance with the next plan, character strengthening that will be done in schools must go through the phases of preparation, implementation, and evaluation of the implementation's results (Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, and Indonesia 2018).

In order to implement the Independent Learning Curriculum in educational units that give students opportunities to develop understanding as part of improving their character and learning opportunities around them (Usman et al. 2023). Activity P5 (Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project) aims to strengthen the Pancasila student profile. Students get practice looking at significant concerns in this P5 exercise. For instance, shifts in radicalism, culture, advertising, technology, etc (Aprila et al. 2024).

By fostering the Pancasila ideals of faith and devotion to God Almighty, global diversity, mutual cooperation, creativity, critical thinking, and independence, the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) helps students grow as individuals. P2RA, on the other hand, is the idea of perspective and attitude to apply the principles of religious moderation. Deliberation (*syurā*), civilised (*ta'addub*), exemplary (*qudwah*), citizenship and nationality (*muwāṭanah*), tolerance (*tasamuh*), fair and consistent (*adil wa i'tidāl*), balanced (*tawazun*), following the middle way (*tawasuth*), equality (*musawwa*), dynamic and inventive (*tathawwur wa ibtikār*), and civilised (*ta'addub*).

By examining the madrasah's conditions, three (three) techniques can be used to execute P5 and P2RA: 1) Co-curricular, in which the project is organised independently of the intracurricular program and selects a theme in accordance with legal requirements. Additionally, 20% to 30% of the total learning hours are allotted for this purpose; 2) P5 and P2RA can work along with intracurricular activities. projects in which topic instructors work together to integrate extracurricular learning activities in order to meet P5 and P2RA requirements. enabling the community to cultivate all-encompassing attitudes and character traits through a variety of problem-based and field learning techniques; 3) In the school's extracurricular activities, P5 and P2RA can be matched. The P5 and P2RA coordinator, the supervisor, and the extracurricular trainers collaborate to create the project (Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Islam 2022).

The following steps must be completed in order to implement P5 and P2RA activities: Creating a Facilitator Team, Assessing the Readiness of Madrasahs, Designing Dimensions, Themes, and Time Allocation (the madrasah's requirements and conditions are taken into consideration when choosing dimensions, values, and themes), assembling a project reporting strategy and project modules (Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Islam 2022).

To differentiate the focus of researchers from others, researchers look at the research results of several other researchers, which are divided into three groups, namely the concept of P5 and P2RA activities, implementation of P5 and P2RA activities, and development of P5 and P2RA activities. Research conducted by (Mallewai 2023), (Fatah et al. 2023), (Sayekti, Hakim, and Anshori 2024) and (Ishaac et al. 2024), examines how the concept of P5 and P2RA activities with school activities, the meaning of the activities carried out, how P5 and P2RA activities maintain traditions and religious containers, and what values are contained in the P5 and P2RA activities.

Research conducted by (Wahyuningsih 2022), (Parjiman et al. 2023), (Anggraini, Jinan, and Ali 2023), (Muthrofin, Ikmal, and Wahyudi 2023), (Fauziah et al. 2023), (Nur'aini 2023), (Dewi 2023), (Aprila et al. 2024), and (Masripah et al. 2024), examined how the implementation of P5 and P2RA activities in schools or madrasahs with themes and forms of activities that each have their own characteristics in the activity process.

Meanwhile, research conducted by (Nugroho 2022), (Akhmadi 2022), (Shodiq 2023), (Mufid 2023), and (Kurniawati et al. 2024), namely how P5 and P2RA can be developed through various activities where these activities are able to be integrated with the concepts or principles of P5 and P2RA. From all the previous studies selected, they are summarized into a table below:

Based on the above mapping, the researcher's research is included in the implementation because the implementation can strengthen the character of the Rahmatan Lil Alamin Student Profile (P2RA) and the Pancasila Student Profile (P5) through a variety of project activities that are tailored to the theme to be taken and the dimensions and values to be instilled.

One of the madrasahs that has begun implementing P5 and P2RA is MA Muhammadiyah 1 in Malang City. The school has carried out initiatives with two themes: Bhinneka Tunggal Ika and Entrepreneurship. The author wishes to know how MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City uses project-based character building, starting with the planning phase, carrying it out, and assessing the project's outcomes, based on the two themes that have been applied.

II. METHODS

This method combines case study research with qualitative research. Case study research is an empirical investigation

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that looks into transient occurrences in a real-world setting. Purposive (as opposed to random) selection of informants or research subjects is required, meaning that it must be done in accordance with study needs or based on knowledge of current variations or elements (Sugiyono 2013). Students, teacher facilitators, and the deputy head of curriculum served as the study's research subjects.

MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City, located in Jl. Baiduri Sepah No.27, Tlogomas, Kec. Lowokwaru, Malang City, East Java 65144, Indonesia, has been selected as the study site. The madrasah has incorporated P5 and P2RA exercises with activities that are consistent with daily life, which is why this location was selected. Information is gathered by means of observation during the activity, interviews with pre-selected research participants, and activity-related supporting documentation (Sugiyono 2013).

The process of making sure the data utilised in a study or analysis is accurate or legitimate is known as data validity testing. The triangulation approach is one of several methods for assessing the veracity of data. This study's researchers employed source triangulation. Researchers use source triangulation to try to get reliable data from multiple sources. It is indicative of a good/good level of validity when the same data is obtained from many sources (Sugiyono 2013).

In order to obtain a thorough understanding, spot patterns or trends, and draw trustworthy conclusions from the data that is currently available, data analysis techniques are employed to conduct systematic analysis. This study's data analysis method is interactive analysis of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana, which includes finding and gathering data, condensing data, presenting data, and making inferences from the data (Miles, Huberman, and Saldana 2014).

III. RESULTS

- a. Organising the P5 and P2RA activities at MA Muhammadiyah 1 in Malang City to improve character.

The curriculum vice principal prepared the planning for P5 (Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project) and P2RA (Rahmatan Lil Alamin Student Profile) by deciding on the activity's time, assembling a team of facilitators, and deciding on a theme. The facilitator in turn created a project module based on the findings of the observations and interviews conducted regarding planning.

- i. Establishing the P5 and P2RA activity times. P5 and P2RA are implemented either once every semester or twice annually. This semester's implementation period is set to begin in October, one month after the PTS (Mid-Semester Assessment), and involves one hour of instruction on theme-related subjects.
- ii. Establishing a team of facilitators. The curriculum vice principal is responsible for

creating a facilitator team after deciding on the implementation date. According to government requirements, the facilitator team that was chosen consists of a teacher whose teaching hours are reported as extra hours for P5P2RA activities. The facilitator team was chosen with the intention of assisting students in carrying out the implementation in the classroom.

- iii. Finding the theme. The facilitator team and the curriculum vice principal then decide on the theme to be used. "Entrepreneurship" is the theme for class 10 this odd semester, whereas "Bhinneka Tunggal Ika" is the theme for class 11. The theme was picked by deciding what values to teach students and because it aligns with the school's closest agenda, which allows the students' project outcomes to be displayed.
 - iv. putting together a project module. The facilitator team is responsible for creating the project module. The project module that was developed includes the preliminary evaluation phase, the activities that were conducted, the theme-appropriate site visits, and the final goods that were to be generated.
- b. MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City's implementation of character strengthening through P5 and P2RA. The facilitator team and students were informed of the findings from the implementation stage observations and interviews. The facilitator team's implementation process followed the original planning or project module, which was broken down into four weeks: the first week was devoted to presenting the materials; the second week was devoted to discussion; and the third and fourth weeks were devoted to product production activities.
 - i. Week-One Each class's facilitator gave an overview of the theme for the semester, the technical implementation, the locations of the trips, and the goods that would be generated during the first week of classes. Following a prologue, the facilitator presented content based on the theme.
 - ii. Week-Two This moved into the core stage in the second and third weeks, when students started to be split up into groups and meet together. They were then given the chance to talk on the goods that would be made in groups.
 - iii. Week-Three Students were given the opportunity to see an ornamental fish farm near Dinoyo this week.

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Pupils are instructed to focus and examine the process of raising ornamental fish.

iv. Week-four

Students are asked to try growing ornamental fish in the last week by following a set of instructions that were demonstrated during yesterday's visit.

- c. An assessment of MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City's use of P5 and P2RA for character development. The curriculum vice principal and the facilitator team were the target audience for the findings of the observations and interviews conducted during the evaluation phase. Here, the facilitator team evaluates how the activity is implemented, whether the final items are completed, and whether or not students exhibit the desired character. In the meantime, the curriculum vice principal's assessment pertains to the full set of P5P2RA implementation activities:

i. Final evaluation.

An evaluation of the complete set of activities is the last one that is conducted. Peer evaluation is the method used to evaluate the students, where a buddy uses the form provided by the class facilitator to rate another friend. Many people are less interested in the activities offered, according to the results of the final assessment on this semester's theme.

ii. Items manufactured

A project activity that results in a piece of work or a product is the P5P2RA activity's output. Class 10 creates items for the entrepreneurial theme, such as hydroponics, ornamental fish farming, and decorative plants, which are on exhibit at the bazaar. At the School Milad event, works of art like as dance performances, plays, and videos are produced around the theme of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika. Obstacles or barriers are encountered by the artwork and merchandise. The cultured fish that were supposed to be on display at the bazaar, for instance, had perished first in the entrepreneurship theme. One of the group members was coerced into participating in the video production despite his reluctance to do so during the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika theme.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the results of the research that has been conducted, the discussion will be focused on several topics:

- a. Organising the P5 and P2RA activities at MA Muhammadiyah 1 in Malang City to improve character.

The character instruction that MA Muhammadiyah 1 provides Through the Rahmatan Lil Alamin

Student Profile (P2RA) and the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5), Malang City is dedicated to implementing character education by all school personnel, including the principal and staff, and reaching an agreement with parents and the community. According to Daryanto (2013), character education encompasses all efforts made by school/madrasa residents in cooperation with parents or guardians and the community to help children and adolescents develop a compassionate, resilient, and responsible mindset.

In addition to government initiatives for character development, schools are dedicated to integrating character education into daily life through P5 (Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project) and P2RA (Rahmatan Lil Alamin Student Profile). Because schools are among the venues where students can learn Islamic teachings, moral principles, and how to live a socially conscious life. This is consistent with Lickona's (1993) view of the importance of character education, which holds that many young generations harm one another due to a lack of moral awareness. Schools play a crucial role as character educators when children receive little moral instruction from their parents, and that successful character education implemented in schools will make schools more civilised, care about society, and refer to an increase in students' academic performance.

The government decided on three strategies for implementing P5P2RA: extracurricular, integrated, and co-curricular. The P5P2RA activity is incorporated into intracurricular activities, namely with other topics, as part of the integrated or integrated activity implemented by MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang. According to the agreement, the facilitators are teachers whose topics are connected to the selected theme. Through field observation or direct instruction, learning is focused on collaborating with the community. Students have the chance to grow in terms of their whole character and attitudes, as well as their potential knowledge and abilities.

The government has offered themes that each educational institution can select from, taking into account the circumstances and environment in which they find themselves. Building your soul and body, Pancasila democracy, engineering and technology to create the Republic of Indonesia, entrepreneurship, employment, sustainable living, local knowledge, and bhinneka tunggal ika are the primary themes. The themes of entrepreneurship for grade 10 and bhinneka tunggal ika for grade 11 were decided upon by MA Muhammadiyah 1

Malang City. Because it aligns with the school's most intimate celebrations, such as the school's Milad and Tabligh Akbar, this motif was selected. where the outcomes of the entrepreneurship theme's products will be displayed, and the outcomes of the *bhinneka tunggal ika* theme's products will be showcased as a performance that fills the event's artistic space.

Forming a facilitator team is the first step in the planning process, which the government has decided must be prepared. The steps involved in becoming a facilitator are as follows: 1) the madrasah head creates a facilitator team; 2) the team is responsible for assembling and executing it for every class; and 3) the facilitator team is assembled with the appointment of a madrasah-level project coordinator, a class or phase-level coordinator or person in charge, and additional members as required.

The head of the madrasah, who is represented by the vice principal of student affairs, is involved in the formation of the facilitator team at MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City. The team then decides on the facilitators for each class and how to organise the activities that will be carried out, ranging from the selected theme to the products that must be produced from this P5P2RA activity. Determining the degree of school readiness is the second planning step. The purpose of this identification is to assess the school's readiness to execute this P5P2RA activity. There are three stages involved in determining readiness: (1) beginning, (2) development, and (3) advanced. Since MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City already has a framework in place to facilitate the implementation of project-based learning, the readiness to carry out P5P2RA activities is the development stage.

Gathering the necessary dimensions, concepts, and time allotment is the third step in the planning process. The constraints and requirements of the school are taken into consideration while choosing dimensions and values, themes, and time allocation. (1) Dimensions, (2) Profile Values, (3) Themes, and (4) Time Allocation are all determined by the facilitator. The entrepreneurship theme for grade 10 at MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City this semester has the dimensions and character values of mutual cooperation, creativity, independence, civility (*ta'addub*), exemplary behaviour (*qudwah*), and deliberation (*syūrā*). The grade 11 theme is *bhinneka tunggal ika*, which has the dimensions and character values of faith and devotion to God Almighty, mutual cooperation,

creativity, civility (*ta'addub*), tolerance (*tasāmuh*), and energy and innovation (*tathawwur wa ibtikār*). Preparing project modules with general stages, such as identifying sub-elements (project objectives), creating subjects, flow, and length, and creating project activities and assessments, is the fourth stage of planning. A group of school facilitators at MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City creates the project modules, which include sub-element selection, activity development, and project evaluations. The stages are tailored to the general stages established by the government.

- b. MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City's implementation of character strengthening through P5 and P2RA.

The government has established principles for adopting P5P2RA, including holistic, contextual, student-centered, exploratory, togetherness, diversity, independence, usefulness, and religion, before beginning the implementation process. The module is implemented in MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City in compliance with the established values, which include student-centredness, exploratoryness, togetherness, variety, usefulness, and religiosity.

Through innovative activities such as creating ornamental plants, hydroponics, and ornamental fish cultivation, which are subsequently sold at a bazaar, the facilitator enhances the qualities of mutual cooperation, creativity, independence, civility (*ta'addub*), exemplary behaviour (*qudwah*), and deliberation (*syūrā*) in relation to the entrepreneurship theme.

Meanwhile, through activities like showcasing artwork that represents solidarity and togetherness, the theme of *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* enhances the qualities of faith and devotion to God Almighty, mutual cooperation, creativity, civility (*ta'addub*), tolerance (*tasāmuh*), and being dynamic and innovative (*tathawwur wa ibtikār*).

- c. An assessment of MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City's use of P5 and P2RA for character development.

Lastly, the module on implementation evaluation states that a final assessment will be conducted at the conclusion of the project. At the conclusion of the project, MA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang City conducted an assessment that included student product results and peer evaluation. The purpose of this peer evaluation is to allow students to evaluate one another and reflect on themselves. Then, in the outcomes of the student-made items, grade 10 students created ornamental fish cultivation, and grade 11 students created artistic

performances. Both the outcomes of the products themselves and the process by which they collaborated to produce results can be used to evaluate the outcomes of these products.

V. CONCLUSION

Several inferences can be made from this study, including:

1. That the government's character development program is project-based, specifically through P2RA (Rahmatan Lil Alamin Student Profile) and P5 (Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project). During the planning phase, the curriculum vice principal, who represents the principle, establishes the implementation schedule, assembles a team of facilitators, chooses a theme, and works with the team to develop a project module. Details of the introduction and presentation to students, group creation and debate, product development, and exhibition are all part of the four-week implementation stage. Peer review is done throughout the evaluation stage to determine whether the final product is successful.
2. Through the Pancasila and Rahmatan lil Alamiin student profiles, the facilitator enhances the qualities of mutual cooperation, creativity, independence, civility (ta'addub), exemplary behaviour (qudwah), and deliberation (syūrā) in the context of the entrepreneurship theme. This is achieved through innovative activities such as the creation of ornamental plants, hydroponics, and ornamental fish cultivation, which are subsequently sold at a bazaar. With activities like showcasing artwork that represents unity, the Bhineka Tunggal Ika theme enhances the qualities of faith and devotion to God Almighty, mutual cooperation, creativity, civility (ta'addub), tolerance (tasāmuh), and dynamic and innovativeness (tathawwur wa ibtikār).
3. Because it engages all body parts—cognitively, affectively, and psychomotorly—project-based character building, as exemplified by P5 and P2RA, can inspire enthusiasm in every student and help them develop the kind of character that the teacher wants.

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